

THE STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGISMS AND THEIR SEMANTIC INVESTIGATION

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Annotation. This article is devoted to the phraseologisms and their semantic investigation. The semantic types of phrases: phraseological unities, phraseological fusions and phraseological combinations have been investigated. Key words: phraseologism, literal meaning, figurative meaning, idioms, collocations, phraseological fusions.

The demand for learning a foreign language in our country is increasing day by day. In particular, there is an increase in the number of the English language learners who act as a bridge between all countries of the world in all fields. For this reason, a lot of attention is being paid to learning a foreign language in Uzbekistan, and it has even been approved by law. This gives even more responsibility to foreign language teachers and specialists who will occupy this field in the future and encourages them to constantly conduct research.[1]

Indeed, phraseology is one of the most difficult areas of foreign language learning. That's why we decided to conduct our next research on phraseologism, and through this research we want to clarify some problems.

Phraseology is a small branch of linguistics, meaning phrase-expression, logos-doctrine. A set of words or a set of sentences with the same meaning as one word is called a phrase. Phraseological units, like lexemes, are divided into two types of meaning:

Literal meaning

1. Figurative meaning

Literal meaning is the meaning of a phraseological unit understood from a book or dictionary.

Figurative meaning is not the meaning that can be understood from the original meaning of a phraseological unit, but it appears as a result of using a phraseological unit in a figurative sense outside of its meaning.

For example, the phraseological unit "the dog ate my homework" has the meaning of good reason for laziness or homework not done on time, this

meaning is the literal meaning of the phraseological unit. Its figurative meaning means excuse for defeat, nonsense.

Semantic classification of phraseological units into types was adopted according to academician Vinogradov's classification of phraseological units in the Russian language. Academician Vinogradov classifies phraseological units as follows:

- 1) Phraseological units (phraseological units)
- 2) Phraseological fusions or idioms
- 3) Phraseological combinations or collocations

Phraseological units (phraseological units) are word units understood from the words in the meaning, they mean a whole and are used figuratively: to play the first fiddle (to be a leader of something), old salt (experienced sailor);

Phraseological fusions or idioms - a phraseological unit whose meaning cannot be understood from the words contained in it and cannot be translated word for word into another language, as well as having a strong phraseological meaning compared to other phraseological units: on Shank's mare (on foot), at sixes and sevens (in a mess).[2]

Academician Vinogradov uses the word idiom as a synonym for phraseology. At the beginning of every idiom lies a certain image. Its formation as an idiom is based on a certain reality. First of all, idiom was invisible as a simple phraseological unit reflected in social practice, the meaning of which is understood from the words in the content. Later, as a result of the disappearance of this specific image, custom or social event, the phraseological unit also loses its meaning value, and it becomes a phraseological unit. When the connection between a specific image and a phraseological unit is lost, it becomes an idiom. There are many such idioms in modern English: to mark time, to get town to bedroom, to stick to one's guns.

We also come across international idioms that were created on the basis of historical evidence, ancient mythology, etc.: Scape goat, Damacles sword, Pandora's box, to pass the Rubison, apple of discord. In addition, there are parallel idioms, which appeared through literal translation: sub rose - under the rose, unter der rose, sons la rose.

Phraseological combinations or collocations are phraseological units whose meaning is easy to understand and which retain their independent meaning and are united based on their original meaning. This group includes:

Fixed conjunctions used with specific ideas: to win victory, to attain success, a delicate subject, a man of honor, to deliver a report, to render assistance

- 1) Pair of synonyms: well and easy, really and truly, hear and soul;
- 2) Foreign words and fixed connections: vale-farewell, habeas corpus, bona fide, faux pas, bon voyage;

Phraseological knowledge in English is divided into semantic structure and structurally by professor Smirnitsky. He divided a group of phraseological units into those that have the same meaning: to give up, to pull out. But to date, a number of Russian linguists consider this group not as a phraseological unit, but as a free association.

It is known that in the 80s of the last century, in the Uzbek linguistic phraseological units, there was a doubt about the tradition of semantically dividing phraseological units into phraseological compounds, phraseological conjunctions and phraseological units. Such work was initiated by academician A.P. Hojiyev. It is said about this: "The components of the meaning expressed by phraseologism are divided into such types as "phraseological combination", "phraseological whole" ("phraseological union"), "phraseological combination" according to the meaning relationship. separated. But such grouping does not have any practical significance. In addition, the words "combination", "integrity", "combination", "confluence" in the above terms do not help to understand the essence of phraseological meaning. In phraseologisms there is no such thing as 'joining', 'interbreeding'.[3]

In fact, it is extremely difficult to divide phraseological units into semantic types based on the classification developed by Academician V.V. Vinogradov, especially to differentiate between phraseological associations and phraseological conflicts. Academician N. M. Shansky also emphasized this in his work. E.V. Kuznesova also tries to prove that there is no strict difference between types of phraseological units such as conjugation and union. Professor A. Nurmonov stated that "in the period of the former Soviets, V.V. Vinogradov's approach to phraseology and its classification into three groups were criticized by a number of experts as being too subjective... The most important thing is that V.V. Vinogradov artificially divided (phraseology) into three the semantic classification of the group is pushed back".

In this sense, the phraseologist A.V. Kunin justified opinions that the author of most English phraseologies is unknown and they were created by the people. However, the origins of some phraseological units can be traced. In this

sense, phraseology is a microsystem that is part of the general system of language, and this system reflects the heritage and values of the past, passed down from generation to generation. Many of the phraseological units that make up a system are a source of enrichment for a particular language. Phraseological system consists of phraseological units, the relationship between their main components.

Phraseologisms are connections of words that consist of more than one word and are stable in meaning and form. Phraseologisms are used in a figurative sense, in figurative expressions, and have norms and methods of historical use, the meaning of which is clarified in a particular speech process. Phraseologisms are different from sentences that are a unit of speech when they are in the form of a phrase or a sentence. As a lexical unit, they are in many ways close to words, and many of the characteristics of words are also characteristic of phraseology. There are different hypotheses in defining the object of phraseology. The object of phraseology consists only of stable combinations.

Phraseology is defined as the study of the spiritual and structural properties of phraseological units, their appearance in the language system, and the properties of their use at a point. Although the term "phraseology" is derived from the Greek word "frama" (phraseos), it is used to mean different things. For this reason, the term phraseology is used in linguistics in two senses: in the general sense of the existing phraseological units in the language, and in the sense of the field that studies such units. So phraseology is the science of expressions. Like other branches of linguistics, phraseology has its stages of formation and development. Although phraseology is very ancient in origin, the science of phraseology spans nearly two hundred years. The founder of the science of phraseology is the Swiss scientist Charles Bally. In his work French Stylistics (1909), he included special chapters on the study of word combinations. Ferdinand de Saussure, on the other hand, expressed his views on syntagma and its features. He said that there are ready-made units in a language whose linguistic nature is due to their meaning and syntactic properties, such combinations are used ready-made, traditionally. Phraseology is one of the fastest growing fields in the further development of linguistics. While phraseology has been studied in Russian and English linguistics for a long time, it has been studied systematically in Uzbek linguistics since the 1940s and 1950s. During this period Sh.Rakhmatullayev

(1969), G.A. Bayramov (1970), G.H. Akhunzyakov (1974), V.G. Uraksin (1975), L.K. Bayramova (1983), M.F. Chernov (1986) are devoted doctoral dissertations to the study of phraseology. The sources of the origin of phraseological combinations in English are very different. It is expedient to study the origin of phraseological combinations in English into three main groups.

1. Old phraseological combinations in English
2. Phraseological combinations learned from other languages
3. Phraseological combinations derived from the American version of English.

The authors of most of the phraseological combinations in English are still unknown to science. This problem is especially evident in articles that are considered to be a type of stable combination. Phraseological combinations in all languages, especially in English, are also folk art that reflects the wisdom and linguistic taste of the nation. Many phraseological units reflect the traditions, customs and beliefs of the English people, historical truths and facts of English history that we know and do not know. The roots of many phraseological units go back to professional communication. The main source of phraseological combinations is the change of their meanings of interconnected words. Many English phraseologies are derived from works of art and various literary sources. According to the number of phraseological combinations in English, after the literary sources, the first place is occupied by the Bible, and the second place is occupied by phraseology from Shakespeare's works. The works of writers, children's poetry, fairy tales, caricatures are also the source of phraseology. V.V. Vinogradov classifies phraseology into three classes: phraseological fusions, phraseological units, phraseological collocations or combinations. Phraseological fusion-components are phraseologies that are not related to the meaning of the whole unit. Phraseological units are made up of words that have a specific valence. One component of such phraseological units is used in its literal sense, the rest in a metaphorical sense. Phraseological units are, to a certain extent, semantically indivisible. For example: heavy father – the main role in the play; to kick the bucket – to die. Phraseologisms such as the bureaucratic method are idioms that have the same meaning as a whole. Phraseological fusion is a completely different meaning of a phrase. But unlike phraseological combinations, their meanings are not understood from the meanings of their components.

Words and phrases from the Bible are widely used in Stoffen's Studies in English, Written and Spoken. In the chapter "Scriptural phrases and Allusions in Modern", the scholar studied biblical phrases and their etymology and made a scientific analysis. The study of biblicalism in Western linguistics is also associated with the name of L.P. Smith. He studied the Bible phrases in his book, *Phraseology of the English Language*. The author writes, "The number of biblical phrases and expressions in English is so great that it is not an easy task to compile and list them". L.P. Smith argues that English contains not only a number of biblical words, but also biblical idiomatic expressions that represent a literal translation of ancient Hebrew and Greek idioms. As a result of the analysis, the following are examples of phraseological combinations with food components related to the Bible:

Adam's apple – a pair of apples;

The apple of Sodom – a beautiful but fresh fruit;

Milk and honey – abundance;

Manna from heaven – waiting anxiously;

A forbidden fruit – a forbidden wet fruit

Biblical Phraseologies English food component phraseologies include food names such as apple, bread, milk, fat and olive. There are also phraseological units associated with place names in English. Their analysis and research can be found in the scientific work of M. Rajabova. The study of place names is considered not only as an object of linguistics, but also as an object of history and geography. One of the current issues of modern linguistics is the study of linguoculturalism in the context of phraseologies that come with place names, to highlight their national and cultural aspects. Examples of place names include the following units: have kissed the Blarney stone – flattering. In Ireland, there is a large stone in front of Blair's castle, and according to English folklore, a person who kisses this stone has a flaw of flattery, laziness; go for a Burton - to die, to turn a blind eye, to disappear without a trace. Barton is a small beer-producing town in Staffordshire. The phrase was first used by British pilots to commemorate their comrades-in-arms who died in World War II. L.P. Smith argues that English contains not only a large number of biblical words, but also biblical idiomatic expressions that represent a literal translation of the ancient Hebrew and Greek idioms. For example, Adam's apple – a phraseological unit with a food component – translates as "to add", "to swallow an apple".

- George entered the office of the property broker, a little bold, old man with a thin neck and prominent Adam's apple. A forbidden fruit is a forbidden wet fruit.[4]

- It is somewhat ironic that many places which need water most critically have here reserves their front yard - California and Texas for example. Yet the salt in the sea water makes it a forbidden fruit. The Bible is the main source for a lot of food-related phraseologies in the Bible. Phraseological fusions are phraseologies in which the meanings of the components are not related to the meaning of the whole unit. For example, heavy father - the main role in a theatrical play, to kick the bucket - to die, red tape - the meaning of bureaucratic methods are phraseologies that give a single meaning that does not depend on the meaning of the words in it. Phraseological fusion is a combination of words whose meaning has changed completely. But unlike phraseological combinations, their meanings are not understood from the meanings of their components, and metaphor-based semantic transitions lose their clarity. Phrases such as to leave somebody in lurch (to abandon a friend when he is in trouble), to show the white feather (to betray one's cowardice), to dance attendance on somebody (to try and attract somebody, to show exaggerated attention) can be an examples. Phraseological combinations are phraseologies whose meaning is understood from the phraseological meaning of whole phraseological units. The transfer of meaning based on metaphor is clear and unambiguous. The lexical components of phraseological combinations are the most stable. Phraseologisms such as "to look a gift horse in the mouth" (to examine a present too critically, to find fault with something one gained without effort), "to ride a high horse" (to behave a superior, haughty, overbearing way), "a big bug" (a person to importance), "a fish out of water" (a person situated uncomfortably outside his usual and proper environment) are examples of phraseological combinations. There is a lot of phraseology. Some of them are easy to translate and some are even international. For example, to know the way the wind blows - to know where the wind blows.

Phraseological units are words that have a specific valence. One component of such phraseological units is used in its literal sense, and the rest is used in a metaphorical sense. Phraseological units are to some extent semantically indivisible. Phraseological units are partially altered combinations of words. The meaning of these phraseological units is easily understood from the meaning of the words that make them up. To be at one's wits end, to be a good hand at something, to come off a poor second, to come to a sticky end, to stick at nothing,

gospel truth, bosom friend are examples of phraseological units. In conclusion, the semantic aspects of occupational phraseological units show that in both languages they are related to human physical labor, which express concepts directly related to human labor activity.[5]

In our opinion, if the semantic classification of phraseologisms is studied in more depth, we think that their practical significance can be clarified. In the future, we will study the semantic differences of phraseologisms and try to put them into practice. In short, by studying phraseology, it is possible to increase the emotional-expressiveness and colorfulness of speech and to eliminate problems related to translation.

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